

A Review Article on *Allium Cepa* Linn.

(ENGLISH NAME ONION BULB)

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English name Onion bulb is found all over India. Leaves are thick round and green with green colored flower stalk at the top. It bears white flowers in clusters. These produce triangular seeds. Flowering and fruiting occur after winter. It contains an oil having pungent taste and offensive smell, sulfur quercetin, silymarin, silymarin, silymarin etc. It acts as an Analgesic, anti-inflammatory, tonic, enhances eye sight and reduces otalgia. Pain due to bronchitis is controlled with a warm poultice of grated onion. In skin infection onion is applied externally as a poultice. In weak eye sight, onion juices mixed with honey is used as eye drop. In ear ache warm onion juices is used as ear drop. It is useful in arthritic pain, sciatica, hysteria, and hydrophobia. It improves digestion and helps in constipation, piles and jaundice, Onions are also used in rectal prolapse cases. It is useful in some cardiac diseases, debility, bleeding disorder, dry cough, dysuria, azoospermia, impotency, dysmenorrhea, cholera, plague, and skin disease.

Onion is used as an antimicrobial, cardiovascular-supportive, hypoglycemic, antioxidant/anticancer, and asthma-protective agent. However, few clinical trials are available to support the use of onion for any indication. In folk medicine, onion has been used for asthma, bronchitis, whooping cough, and similar ailments. Other uses include the treatment of stingray wounds, warts, acne, Loss of appetite, urinary tract disorders, and indigestion. Onion skin dye has been used as an egg and cloth coloring.

(Blumenthal M. et al 1999), Fresh onion bulbs are used at daily doses of 50 g; dried onion is used at a dose of 20 g/day for dyspepsia. Contraindications have not yet been identified.

Generally recognized as safe for use as food. Avoid dosages above those found in foods because safety and efficacy are unproven.

The Complete German Commission E Monographs lists no contraindications, side effects, or interactions. The reputed toxicity of large doses of onion has been unresolved.

(Ensminger et al; 1994, Dwyer I et al; 1986, Bluementhal sr. ed et al; 1998 and Fleming et al; 1998), Observed that the onion plant is a perennial herb growing to about 1.2 m, with 4 to 6 hollow, cylindrical leaves. On top of the long stalk, greenish-white flowers are present in the form of solitary umbels growing up to 2.5 cm wide. The seeds of the plant are black and angular. The underground bulb, which is used medicinally, is comprised of fleshy leaf sheaths forming a thin-skinned capsule. The onion is one of the leading vegetable crops in the world.

(Fleming et al; 1998), The onion is believed to have been domesticated in central Asia. Onions were used as early as 5,000 years ago in Egypt, as depicted on ancient monuments; ancient Greek and Roman records also refer to the onion.

(Ensminger et al; 1994 and Dwyer I et al; 1986), During the Middle Ages, onions were consumed throughout Europe. They later were thought to guard against evil spirits and the plague, probably because of their strong odor.

(Schulz V et al; 1998), Onion skin dye has been used for egg and cloth coloring for many years in the Middle East and Europe. Columbus was said to have brought the onion to America. Folk healers used the onion to prevent infection. The combination of onions and garlic cooked in milk is a European folk remedy used to clear congestion. Onions also are used in homeopathic medicine.

(Ensminger et al; 1994, Dwyer I et al; 1986, Bluementhal sr. ed et al; 1998 and Fleming et al;1998), Onions contain 89% water, 1.5% protein, and vitamins, including B1, B2, and C along with potassium. Polysaccharides such as fructose's, saccharose, and others are also present, as are peptides, flavonoids, and essential oil.

(Bluementhal sr. ed et al; 1998, Fleming et al;1998 and Schulz V. et. Al; 1998), Onion contains alliin and similar sulfur compounds, including allylalliin and methyl and propyl compounds of cysteine sulfoxide.

(Bandyopadhyay C et al;1970), Sulfur and other compounds of *A. cepa* have been analyzed. The flavor components of onion have been evaluated by thin-layer chromatography.

(Al-Nagdy S et al; 1986), Prostaglandins also have been identified in onion, and onion cell wall analyses have been performed. The chemical analysis of onion seed oil is available.

(Bluementhal sr. ed et al; 1998), Onion has shown antibacterial, **(Guarrera P M et al;1999)** antiparasitic, **(Dankert J et al;1979 and Zohari An et al;1995)** and antifungal actions.

Salmonella typhimurium mutagenicity was reduced in hamburger when onions were added. **(Kim Jhet al; 1997)** Growth of oral pathogenic bacteria, including *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus subbrings*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, and *Prevotella intermedia*, the main causes of dental caries and periodontitis, was prevented by onion extracts.

(Dankert J et al;1979 Zohari An et al;1995 and Elnima eI et al;1983), Onion juice or oil also have inhibited growth of other gram-positive bacteria and the gram-negative bacterium *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

(Dankert J et al;1979), Antifungal actions of onion include inhibition of yeasts,

(Zohari An et al;1995), Microspore Canis, Microsporium gypseum, Trichophyton semi, Trichophyton mentagrophytes, Chrysosporium queenslandicum, Aspergillus flavus, and Penicillium rubrum. (Fleming et al;1998) One source identifies the thiosulfate principle in the onion as a main antimicrobial agent.

(Goldman II et al; 1996), Certain onion genotypes containing higher contents of sulfur in the bulb correlated with greater antiplatelet activity.

(Fleming et al;1998 Miller Lget al;1998), Thiosulfates dimethyl- and diphenylthiosulfinate, for example, are known to retard thrombocyte biosynthesis.

(Makheja Anet al;1979), The least polar fraction of onion extract was associated with the most inhibitory activity toward platelet aggregation; thus, a greater inhibition of thromboxane synthesis was reported.

(Ali M et al; 1990), Synthesis of thromboxane's and prostaglandins in vitro has been shown with onions, as well as with garlic and other Liliaceae family members.

(Augusti K.T et al ;1974, Wilcox BF et al; 1984, Sebastian K.L. et al; 1979, Lata S. et al; 1991 and Kumari K et al 1995), The hypolipidemic effects of sulfur-containing principles in onion, including S-methyl cysteine sulfoxide and allyl propyl disulfide, have been demonstrated in several studies in rats and rabbits.

(Lata S. et al;1991), Examples include onion's protective effects against diet-induced atherosclerosis, and its marked action in controlling lipids and triglycerides. Cardiovascular disease risk factors also involve blood coagulability. Several reports confirm the onion's inhibitory effects on platelet formation.

(Boradia et al; 1996 and Chen JH et al; 2000), Onion demonstrated antithrombotic effects in rats.

(Ali M et al; 1990), Dose-dependent inhibitory effects on platelet aggregation with raw onion also were seen in rabbits.

(Boradia et al; 1996), Boiling onion may cause decomposition of the antithrombotic ingredient.

(Doutremepuich C, et al 1985), One report evaluates onion's hemostatic effects in humans, but certain lipid-reducing and blood pressure-lowering effects in humans have not yet been clinically proven. (Fleming et al;1998) Onion's benefits relating to cardiovascular disease have been reviewed.

(Galal EE et al; 1965, Augusti et al; 1973 and Kumari et al; 1975) Studies from 1965 to 1975 report antidiabetic activity, "hypoglycemic principles," and blood sugar level reduction in diabetic rabbits.

(Roman Romas R et al; 1995), More recent reports confirm many of these claims, finding similar outcomes. Onion decreased the hyperglycemic peak in rabbits.

(Kumari K et al 1995 and Sheela et al; 1995), In addition, onion amino acid s-methyl cysteine sulfoxide contributed to antidiabetic effects in affected rats, controlling blood glucose in addition to other diabetic effects comparable to insulin.

(Bratman S et al; 1997), Although more research is needed on the use of onion as a treatment for diabetes in humans, many articles describe its benefits in improving glucose levels.

(Fukushima S et al; 1997), Onion has proven to be an antioxidant and may be beneficial in certain cancers. The organosulfur compounds contained in onion exert chemo preventive effects on chemical carcinogenesis. The constituent diallyl disulfide possesses inhibitory properties against colon and renal cancers. (Helen A, et al;1999) Oil

of onion is an effective antioxidant against nicotine-induced damage in rats. (Winter R et al; 1995) People consuming diets high in allium vegetables, including onion, suffer from fewer incidences of stomach cancer.

(Challier B et al;1998), Onion's protective factors for breast cancer have been evaluated in a case-control study in France. (Paganga G et al; 1999) Another report compares the antioxidant activity of onion polyphenols with those of other fruits and vegetables.

(MacAnlis GT et al; 1999), The quercetin component in onion, however, was found to be absorbed by humans from dietary sources but provided no direct protective effect during low-density lipoprotein oxidation.

(Whiting S.D. et al; 1998, Ensgimnger et al; 1994, Dwyer I et al; 1986. Bluementhal sr. ed et al; 1998, Fleming et al;1998 and Bratman S et al; 1997), Folk medicine has used the onion for treatment of asthma, whooping cough, bronchitis, and similar ailments. The onion is used in homeopathic medicine.

Onion juice administration protected guinea pigs from asthma attacks. An ethanol extract of onion reduced allergy-induced, bronchial constriction in certain patients. The thiosulfates present in the onion are said to inhibit bronchoconstriction, but definite efficacy remains unproven in this area.

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